

Ref. number: A011

Date: 1st January 2022

Subject: Approval Decision
To: Nada Kadum Jawad,

The Research Ethics Committee has received a request for ethical approval for the following research:

Research No.	11
Approval No.	A011
Project title	The effect of working in Gasoline station with serum levels of lead and other related biomarkers – a cross sectional study
Decision	Approved

According to the revision by the committee (please tick the proper decision):

☒	The research ethics committee gave approval to the research
☐	The research ethics committee gives approval to the research after completing the required corrections
☐	The research ethics committee refused the research

Ass. Prof. Dr. Ahmad Tarik Numian

Chairman of the Research Ethics Committee

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